

Effect of Price, Promotion, Location and Interest Buy as Variable Moderation to Decision Purchase of Cendana Homes Property at PT. Lippo Karawaci

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Abstract:- The Covid 19 pandemic is not just a pandemic but also became a catalyst for various business lines to innovate in order to survive and compete with competitors, Bank Yudha Bhakti now known as Bank Neo Commerce (BNC) is one of the banks that took the Rebranding to deal with Covid 19 exposure. thus the objective of this research is to find out how far the change in name, logo, slogan and service has affected the company's image for BNC KCU Jakarta Gozco customers. Some of the theories that serve as tools in this research are systems theory which explains that rebranding or changes that occur within the organization as a result of environmental influences at the same time assessed as an adaptation mechanism which is clarified by organizational communication theory and corporate image theory in the context of corporate communication goals towards external audiences to meet customer expectations. This study uses rebranding as an independent variable they are Name, Logo, Slogan and Service on its influence on Company Image as Variable Y. This study used a quantitative approach with a survey method by distributing questionnaires to 180 samples. The type or nature of this research is associative, causal, in this study BNC wants to convey its goal that they have turned into a digital bank through rebranding. The conclusion of this study is that the significance value for the Name variable (X1) to Image (Y) is $0.357 > 0.05$ and the t-count value to the t table of Name Variable (X1) is $0.923 < 1.973$ so that the name change has no significant effect, then for the Variable Logo (X2) has a significant value of $0.429 > 0.05$ and the value of t count to t table is $0.793 < 1.973$ in other words changes in the logo do not significantly affect the BNC image, then Slogan (X3) has a significant value of $0.02 < 0.05$ while the t count value for the t table is $3.175 > 1.973$ so that changes in the Slogan have a significant effect on the Image of the Neo Commerce Bank, Service

(X4) gets a significant value of $0.00 < 0.05$ and the t count value on the t table is $3.958 > 1.973$ so that the change in Slogan has a significant effect to the BNC Image, then simultaneously neously X1, X2, X3, and X4 to Y have a significant value of $0.000 < 0.005$ and a calculated F value of $39.702 > 2.42$ it can be concluded that the change in Name, Logo, Slogan, and Services simultaneously have a significant effect on the BNC Image of Jakarta Gozco KCU customers.

Keyword: Rebranding, Corporate Image, Bank Neo Commerce.

I. INTRODUCTION

PT. Lippo Karawaci is developer home made _ property residential and commercial . Characteristics offer part big marketing housing area almost identical . PT. Lippo Karawaci make an effort offer housing , for one called Housing area Sandalwood Homes. Residential This own excess that is affordable , have attractive design , located in a strategic location , and has complete facilities . _ As developer Housing area Sandalwood Homes, PT. Lippo Karawaci No only limited make home , but also tried For get customer and change behavior they so that they buy product . Sale product , fine Now and in the future , are strongly influenced by behavior and attitudes consumer.

According to data from Real Estate Indonesia (REI), there is other developers in the regency and city of Tangerang apart from PT. Lippo Karawaci . At least a number of developer big other currently build housing in Banten, so Lots competition in the real estate industry . For fulfil needs and wants the customer , PT. Lippo Karawaci must pay attention to it . Table 1 displays information about developer in Tangerang:

Table 1 Developer (*Developer*) in Tangerang

No	Developers	Clusters	Location
1	Lippo Land	Sandalwood Homes Seris	Karawaci
2	Sinar Mas Land	Earth Serpong peace	Serpong
3	Paramound Land	Milano Village	Ivory Serpong
4	Summarecon Serpong	Leonora Symphonia	Ivory Serpong
5	Ciputra	Great Image	Cikupa
6	Purinusa Jaya Kusuma	Aryana Karawaci	Binong
7	Harasuma Prosperous _	Summa Village Karawaci	Binong
8	Prosperous Paramound	Paramound Petals	waterfall
9	BSA Land	Goldend Stones	legok

Source: REI Property Tangerang-Banten info 2022

Table.1 Show sector *property* Still promising in the midst of the *Covid-19* pandemic seen from *subsector property* to be pusher growth economy that is *sector property*. *Subsector* the is House site . this _ seen from enhancement sale a number real estate companies , in particular Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci , which shows that desire public For own House the more increase . Sales in 2022 were driven by the launch of a successful housing project for homeowners consisting of Cendana

Homes from Icon Sandalwood, Marq Sandalwood, Nest Sandalwood, Clov’r Sandalwood and Gard’n Sandalwood in Karawaci, as well as Diponogoro and Himalayan Brava Sandalwood . This launch saw an acceptance rate of over 95%. The first home owner segment contributed 64.3% to total marketing sales in Year 20 22. Demand for older completed projects (launch before 2019) also increased in early 20 22, with total sales of IDR 132 billion.

Table 2 Sale House Sandalwood Home perCluster for 2019-2022

Year	Sales Target (Per Unit)	Realization (Unit)	Achievement (%)	Information
2019	496	496	100%	sold out
2020	789	775	98%	14 units remaining
2021	779	755	96%	24 units remaining
2022	1,250	1235	95%	15 units remaining
Total	3,314	3,281	97%	Remaining 33 Units

Source: PT. Lippo Karawaci

Based on Table 2, realization sales achieved _ every the year during four year final Not yet achieve the desired target. During four year Finally, the average target achievement reaches 97% or only 3,281 units of the target of 3,314 units. Achievement highest 98% in 2020, and achievements lowest 95% in 2022. Peak sale happening in

2020 , and developer only stay use up remainder stock in two years next (Aveliable stocks) because happened Covid 19 meanwhile developer currently finish development in the region Sandalwood Homes between 2019 to 2022. This thing lead to target and realization sale House decreased.

Table 3 Type House Sandalwood Homes Based on Selling Price Year 2019-2022

Type	Number of units	Land area	Building Area	Price
Type 1	1,368	60m	55m	751,000,000
Type 2	1,520	82.5 m	68m	1,061,000,000
Type 3	426	97.5 m	88m	1,223,000,000

Source: PT. Lippo Karawac

For maintain existence in face increasing competition _ tight and tight , PT. Lippo Karawaci Keep going develop self through various initiative exciting promotion _ interest buy society and influence decision purchase . At Lippo Karawaci, interest public For buy enough real estate big .

this _ can concluded from results ten interview beginning researcher with a number customer stated _ interest For buy real estate products for get right ownership property For need house (board) and for future investment. Among them is as following :

Table 4 Promotion Strategy Sandalwood Homes Based Promotion Program

No	Promotion Program	Information
1	Proliferation advertisement through Lots account on the trading platform prepaid	Yes
2	Participate in exhibition property or interesting exhibition _ Lots visitors	No
3	Facebook, Instagram, YouTube and social media platforms other spread advertisement	Yes
4	Provide catalog products sold _	Yes
5	Installation Billboards , banners , billboards in several point strategically in the Lippo Karawaci area .	Yes
6	Giving Discount	Yes
7	Giving gimix in the form of AC, Hypermart Vouchers , Living Room Vouchers	Yes
8	Giving Dorprize Promos	No
9	Ease of KPR without 0% DP	Yes
10	Providing Free Program Cost mortgage contract	Yes

Source : Activities Promotion Lippo Karawaci

Based on description above _ so need done pre – survey of variables the. Pre-survey was conducted with distributed questionnaires _ through electronic media that is *Google Forms*. Questionnaire distributed in 10 Statements respondent shows the data obtained from results deployment *questionnaire pre -survey*.

Result of four the variables tested in *pre -survey* obtained three variable that has mark highest , namely Price, Promotion , and Location in marketing House *Sandalwood Homes* . Study This aim For know problems that occur in the field related with Selling Prices , Promotions and the Environment House *Sandalwood Homes Series* at PT. Lippo Karawaci . Frequent situations _ appear is when price sell No in accordance with promotions being intensified by entrepreneurs in the industry property this . Promotion the utilise brochure presented _ side by side with home models minimalism makes it looked pretty . Brochures are also promising good facilities in the neighborhood around which not compared straight with what happened on the ground . as a result customer become No satisfied Because No can enjoy attractive home models and facilities _ promised flagship _ company . Consequently , they must promoted through social media or digital marketing.

II. LITERATURE REVIEWS

A. Properties:

➤ *Understanding Properties:*

According to definition dictionary , the word “ property “ comes from from the word language English “ *property* “; meaning something that can owned by someone . Example property covers land , buildings , facilities , and infrastructure constituting part important from land or the building in question , that is land and buildings owned by alone . A number of type building used _ in the real estate industry are :

- Building commercial (*commercial building*),
- Building housing (*residential*)
- building (*industrial building*)
- Building facility public (*public facilities*)

B. *Theory Behavior Consumer:*

- Theory about behavior consumer can broken down become four category :
- Microeconomic Theory- According to Adam Smith’s theory of growth economy based on ideas that people act in accordance with interests Alone every when .
- Theory Psychological- Theory psychology This built on top factor psychological persistent individual_ influenced by power environment.
- Theory Sociological- Theory psychology social is another name for theory this. Theory This more focus on how people’s behavior is influenced by the relationship between them .
- Theory Anthropologist- Due to factors This play role important in formation attitude and is indicator from the values will be adopted consumer, theory This emphasize behavior _ purchase group of people, incl culture , subculture , and class social .

C. *Draft Behavior Consumer (Consumer Behavior):*

Behavior consumer (*consumer Behavior*) is studies about How somebody or individual , group , and organization use choose , buy , and how goods , ideas, and services or experience For satisfying wants and needs them .

➤ *Mix Marketing (Marketing Mix):*

Marketing Mix is gathering variable marketing controlled use _For reach objective target market marketing. The four P’s (*product, place, price, promotion*) are variables that impact the mix marketing. Reference / mix strategy is the most important from these four strategies Because everything own impact One each other.

• *Purchase Decision:*

✓ *Interest Buy:*

Kotler, Bowen, and Makens said that after there is an evaluation process alternative , then There is interest buy . Somebody will make series choice about product to be bought during the evaluation process based on brand or request . (Kotler, Bowen and Makens, 2014)

✓ *Factor Interest Buy:*

Forming factors _ interest buy consumer according to Kotler, P. 2013 namely ; Attitudes of others, Factor situation that is not anticipated.

Benjamin Molan translate a 2014 Kotler article that states that the AIDA stimulus model is indicator interest buy : Focus (concentration) , Intention , Desire , Action.

D. Draft Satisfaction Customer:➤ *Satisfaction Customer:*

In Book Management Marketing , Kotler and Keller say that satisfaction customer is feeling like or disappointment comes from from compare performance something product with what to expect from him . (Rahmawati , 2013)

According to Kotler 2013, measurement level satisfaction consumer can done with way ; System complaints and suggestions , Survey satisfaction customer , customer shadow (also known as “ghost shopping”), Analysis switching customer (also known as as “ analysis lost customer “)

Potential aspect _ affect satisfaction customer in a manner effective including the following : Fees warranty , Handle complaint customers , Market Position , Cost quality low , Industry publications

➤ *Satisfaction Level Consumer:*

There are five aspects main satisfaction a must customer Note: Quality Product, Quality Service, Emotional, Price, Cost.

➤ *Indicator Satisfaction:*

Indicator Satisfaction Customer according to (Kotler & Keller, 2016) attributes formation satisfaction customer consists from: Satisfaction with Hope, Desire to Return, Willingness For Recommend

E. Draft Management Marketing:➤ *Understanding Management Marketing:*

Tjiptono and Chandra (2016) stated that management marketing is system operation comprehensive business intended _ For plan, determine price, and distribute goods, services, and concepts that can be satisfying target market needs For reach objective organization.

➤ *Basic Concepts of Management:*

There are five concepts guiding marketing - How business do activity marketing them, and concepts This

changed along time. Development of these ideas from beginning until moment.

This will explained as following:

- Production Idea
- Product Idea
- Sales Idea
- Marketing Idea
- Marketing Idea Social.

➤ *Function Marketing:*

Covers Function Exchange With marketing, function Distribution Physical , Function Intermediary.

➤ *Task Marketing:*

Following This is a number of task marketing : Introducing Product, Reach Target Sales, Ensuring Satisfaction Customer, Develop Advanced Strategy, Work with Marketing Partners , Create Recapitulation Sale.

➤ *Marketing Strategy:*

Strategy at first used For win war . Next , the strategy used by a number organization in general with still maintain understanding original ; Whereas its application customized with type the organization implementing the strategy with explanation of the five P’s, namely strategy is : planning (*plan*), pattern (*patter n*), position (*potition*), perspective (*perspective*), game (*play*)

F. Sales Volume:➤ *Understanding Sale:*

Purpose sale is look for buyer , influence them , and give they instructions for them can change need them to fit with product offered and agreed _ favorable price _ second split party . On the other hand, according to Kotler (2016), it is a social process in which individuals or group in a manner free offer For exchange valuable product _ with other party use obtain something they _ need or want.

Get profit from sale something product or goods is objective main from sales .

- Factors Sale In practice , activity sale That influenced by several factor as following : Conditions and Capabilities Seller , Market Conditions , Capital , Conditions Company Organization .
- Types Sale that is Sale cash (cash sales, Sales credit (*sales on account*)

Fig 1 Thinking Framework Diagram
Source: Researcher (2022)

III. METHODS

This study uses quantitative methods and causal associative research to conduct research. This study uses causal associative research to find out how much the intention to buy a Cendana Homes house and customer satisfaction at Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci are influenced by price, location and promotion. The independent variable of this research is (X) which includes: Location (X3), Promotion (X2), and Price (X1). Purchase intention (Y) is the dependent variable of the study. Purchase decision (Z) is a research intervening variable. The following table provides a more in-depth view of how the variables in this study are operationalized:

Table 5 Operational Variables

Variable	Dimensions	Indicator
Price (X1) Kotler and Armstrong	a. Affordable price b. Prices are appropriate quality c. Prices are appropriate with benefit d. Prices are appropriate Power competitive price	1. I can buy House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci offered by Marketing Lippo Karawaci . 2. According i , price House Sandalwood Homes is appropriate with Need public Millennials In particular . 3. I don't object with price House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci Because in accordance with conditions and abilities I 'm improving . 4. According I price House Sandalwood Homes is competitive with House around Tangerang area.
Promotion (X2) Kotler and Keller	a. Advertising b. Marketing Direct c. Promotion Sale d. Public Relations e. Personal Sales	1. I know information House Sandalwood Homes from Internet Promotional Media 2. I get offer interesting that is Discount Price _ 3. I follow activities held _ sandalwood homes like follow NUP bookings and Launching events price prime 4. Team Promotion do the Event Stand booth at the Show Unit location 5. I get complete information _ around feature promotion via IG, Whatsup , Email.
Location (X3)	a. Reliability (Reliability) b. Tangibles (Physical Evidence) c. Responsiveness _ _ d. Superiority e. Empathy (Empathy)	1. According I am Home Marketing Sandalwood Homes can submit Location with clear and thorough and also skilled in Offer Product House Sandalwood Homes. 2. Home Sandalwood Homes has a very strategic location near with Toll, Mall, House hospitals , places of worship and education . 3. Marketing of Sandalwood Homes is capable handle problem

		<p>complaint consumer with precise and professional.</p> <p>4. Marketing Sandalwood Homes explains to I in a manner detail about Environment and location Sandalwood Homes without requested .</p> <p>5. Marketing Sandalwood Homes is not looked rank / social status but based on condition buyer .</p>
Interest purchase (Z) Philip Kotler	<p>a. Attention</p> <p>b. Interest</p> <p>c. Desire</p> <p>d. Action</p>	<p>1. I'm looking for know Quality Location and <i>Specifications</i> Building through electronic media and the internet.</p> <p>2. I collect information and compare facility service and Location with other .</p> <p>3. I have desire For use service Sale House Sandalwood Homes because in accordance need finance i .</p> <p>4. I decided For use Buy House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci .</p>
Purchase decision (Y) Kotler & Keller	<p>a. Conformity of Expectations</p> <p>b. Interest Visit Back</p> <p>c. Willingness recommend</p>	<p>1. Marketing services provided make condition desire I the more Certain so that I refer to friends , so I feel satisfied Buy at Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci .</p> <p>2. I feel satisfied with marketing services provided , so I will Keep going use service the marketing service For buy Back Sandalwood Homes.</p> <p>3. I will recommend to brothers and relatives For use service Marketing services at Lippo Karawaci .</p>

The population in this research is all the Buyers of Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci. The criteria for the number of samples used in the *Structural Equation Modeling* (SEM) analysis are adjusted to the number of samples used in the study. In this study, the minimum number of respondents for the sample was 135. Purposive sampling was used as a non-probability sampling method in this study. Accidental sampling is used as a non-probability sampling method. Accidental sampling was used in this study to collect data, in this study there were several criteria including the following:

- Consumers who have purchased Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci.
- Buyers aged 22 years to 55 years.
- Buyers with conditions that allow when will fill out the questionnaire.
- Buyer's Assistant if the buyer is not able to fill out the questionnaire.

The respondents who were sampled were Lippo Karawaci Sandalwood Homes Consumers from August 2019 to December 2022. The data collection method utilized primary and secondary data.

- *The research instrument is placed first before the analysis of each variable can begin:*
 - Validity Test: Confirmatory factor analysis was used to determine the validity of the study.
 - Reliability Test: Cronbach's Alpha is the method that will be used in this study to test reliability.

➤ *The data that needs to be analyzed are the results of field research surveys and literature. After that, a conclusion analysis was carried out. The following is the order of analysis:*

- Researchers collect data.
- Identify the measurement tools used to collect data from the subject matter of the investigation. The list of statements or questionnaires is the measuring tool referred to in this study.
- Next, distributing the survey to Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci. The author has given a score of one to five for each positive statement on the questionnaire items. After that, the list of questions from the questionnaire was given to the selected section. There are five answers to each question on this survey, each with a different value or score for each positive statement.
- Once collected, the data is processed, analyzed and presented in tabular form. Researchers used statistical tests in this study. The analysis used to evaluate the variables X, Y, and Z is based on the average (mean) of each variable. By adding up the total of each variable and dividing it by the number of respondents, the average value is obtained.

Researchers in this study used SmartPLS 3.3 software to measure research data using the Partial Least Square (PLS) method and IBM SPSS Statistics 26 software to analyze descriptive characteristics. Model measurement (inner model), model structure (outer node), and testing are the first steps in the testing process. Descriptive analysis can be divided into two parts: Description of respondents and variables In general, there are several steps in using SEM, namely as follows: Model specification, Free Parameter Estimation, Fit Evaluation, Model Modification, Communication and Interpretation, Replication, and Revalidation.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

$$P = \frac{5 - 1}{5} = 0,8$$

A. Results:

➤ Characteristics of Respondents:

There are four units for descriptive analysis of respondent data, each containing the following information:

The results showed that the majority of respondents or as many as 87 people or 64.44% answered male, while 48 people or a small number of respondents answered female (35.56%). Based on the respondent's last education, characteristics. The results showed that the majority of respondents or as many as 100 people answered undergraduates (74.07%). SMA was answered by a small number of respondents, at least three people or 2.22%. Characteristics of respondents related to work. The results showed that as many as 89 people or 65.93% of those surveyed answered as private employees. While traders were answered by a small portion of respondents, namely as many as six people or 4.44%. Respondent characteristics related to age. Based on the research findings that have been conducted, the majority of respondents answered between the ages of 20 and 30 years or as many as 101 people or (74.81%). However, a small proportion of respondents, at least 11 or 8.15%, provided information that was older than 40 years.

➤ Instrument Test Study:

• Validity Test:

Pearson Product Moments is method correlation used _ in study This For determine whether the item statement is valid or not. It is possible for interesting conclusion that statement of items considered is reliable construction _ If mark coefficient the correlation more big from mark critical 0.3. Test results validity instrument to fifth variable study can seen from results research . All statement items own coefficient more validity _ big from critical 0.3, which indicates that item _ worthy used as tool measuring research and get used For analysis more carry on based on findings the . So that can pulled conclusion that each statement item has declared valid and can used in analysis next .

• Reliability Test:

Instrument tested its reliability one time, then analyzed use Alpha-Cronbach method. If the coefficient reliability questionnaire more big of 0.7, then considered reliable. Reliability test produce results as following: Based on findings study regarding the reliability test questionnaire. this _ proven that details statement own mark reliability more big from 0.7 to fifth the variables studied . Based on findings such, statement items questionnaire can dependable For measure variable.

➤ Analysis Descriptive Research Data:

Evaluation the own mark a maximum of five and a minimum value of one in the study this , so If mark the summed up with equality previously so obtained results as following :

Based on results calculation long class every interval, can known in the calculations above mark range class on each category that is of 0.8.

• Response Respondents About Variable Price (X_1):

Respondents' average response to the price variable (X1) can be seen in the seven statement items that make up the price variable (X1). The total score is 3708, and the average value of respondents' responses to the price variable (X1), which is 3.92, is included in the appropriate category. The continuum line for the variable Price (X1) reveals the score interpretation criteria for the variable Price (X1). The average value of 3.92 which is in the range of 3.40 to 4.20 indicates that the respondent's response is included in the appropriate category. The conclusion that can be drawn from these results is that the respondents' responses to the price variable (X1) fall into the appropriate category.

• Response Respondents About Variable Promotion (X_2):

Based on findings research , the average response respondent to variable Promotion (X2) gain total score of 4295 with category " good ". Besides that is , the average value of the responses respondent to variable Promotion (X2) of 3.98. Research results show that response respondent including in category well proven _ with the average value of which is 3.98 in range 3.40 to 4.20. Criteria interpretation score For variable Promotion (X2) got seen in relation with a continuum line on the variable Promotion (X2). Possible conclusion pulled from results the is that response respondent to variable Promotion (X2) included in category ok.

• Response Respondents About Variable Location (X_3):

In the variable Location (X3) with a total of eight statement items. The overall score is 4215, and the average value of respondents' responses to the location variable (X3) is 3.90 which is included in the good category. The continuum line on the location variable (X3) and the score interpretation criteria for that variable. The results showed that the respondents' responses were included in the "good" category with an average value of 3.90 which was in the range of 3.40 to 4.20.

• Response Respondents About Variable Interest Buy (Z):

With a total of five statement items on the variable Purchase Interest (Z). The average respondent's response to the variable Purchase Interest (Z) can be seen from the results. The overall score is 2649, and the average value of respondents' responses to the variable Purchase Interest (Z) is 3.92 which is high. The continuum line on the variable Interest to Buy (Z) and the score interpretation criteria for that variable (Z). The results showed that the respondents' responses were included in the high category with an average value of 3.92 which was in the range of 3.40 to 4.20.

• *Response Respondents About Variable Purchase Decision (Y):*

With a total of four statement items on the Purchase Decision variable (Y). The results showed that the average respondent gave a total score to the Purchase Decision variable (Y) of 2116, and the average value of their response

to the Purchase Decision variable (Y) was 3.92 which was included in the good category. Based on the results of the continuum line variable Purchase Decision (Y). The results showed that the respondents' responses were included in the "good" category with an average score of 3.92 which was in the range of 3.40 to 4.20.

➤ *Analysis Statistics verification:*

This related with equation modeling _ structural in analysis verification this. The next PLS-SEM method will used For test hypothesis in this model. The PLS-SEM model used in study This shown below _ this.

Fig 2 PLS-SEM Model Conceptual Diagram
The SmartPLS 3.0 program application is used for the PLS-SEM model calculation process.

➤ *Testing Outer Model (Measurement Model):*

• *Convergent Validity:*

Output from model testing is as following , based on results the estimates obtained with help application program SmartPLS 3. All variable manifest (observation) has more loading factor values big of 0.70, accordingly with results model testing . because _ That validity construct for the SEM-PLS model it says high . The loading factor value of each variable show that all loading factors are valuable more from 0.70. Consequently , every construct study own high validity , as can be _ concluded . After That will *the average variance extract (AVE)* test was carried out for more strengthen findings validity converge . According to Hair et al. (2019), the construct used in study considered valid if more AVE value big from 0.5. this _ proven from results that the average variance is extracted give base For results validity converge . All latent variable has more AVE value big of 0.5 , as the findings suggest . If seen from mark extracted mean variance , p This show that indicators composer latent constructs have validity good convergence .

➤ *Discriminant Validity Test:*

The cross loading value shows validity discriminant . In Ghozali (2014:45), Fornell and Larcker (1981) set that mark correlation indicator with construct must more big from mark correlation indicator with construct other . Findings show that , compared with construct others , there are strong correlation _ between all indicators and

constructs . As a result , got pulled conclusion that research model own validity high discrimination _ For Effect No Direct specific .

➤ *Reliability Test:*

Cronbach's Alpha and *Composite Reliability* used For determine is *construct reliability* adequate or no . *Cronbach's Alpha* and *Composite Reliability* must more big of 0.70 order construct considered reliable (Hair et al., 2017), but although more big of 0.60, construct the Still fulfil condition as reliable. Findings show exists latent construct with more Cronbach's alpha value big of 0.6, indicating high reliability. _ Besides that, all mark reliability composite more latent constructs big from 0.60. this _ show that models can be dependable blessing mark the reliability of alpha and Cronbach composite obtained .

➤ *Structural Model Testing (Inner Model):*

Inspection results from connection between construct is evaluation to the inner models. R square, f square, relevance predictive Q-square, and testing hypothesis is component deep model testing.

• *R Square:*

In addition, based on the results of the SmartPLS 3 test, the R Square results were obtained with 0.67 representing a strong model, 0.33 representing a moderate model, and 0.19 representing a weak model. Table 4.37 shows that the variable Purchase Interest (Z) has an R-

Square of 0.978. This shows that Price (X1), Promotion (X2), and Location (X3) have a combined effect on Purchase Intention (Z) of 97.8%, while other variables not examined in this study have an effect of 2.2%.

The Purchase Decision Variable (Y) has an R-Square of 0.972 which indicates that Price (X1), Promotion (X2), and Location (X3) have a combined effect of 97.2 percent on Purchase Decision (Y) through Purchase Interest (Z), while the remaining 2.8% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

• *f Square:*

The results obtained from the F Square variables Price (X1), Promotion (X2), and Location (X3) each have a moderate effect on the Purchase Intention (Z) variable based on the results of the SmartPLS 3 test. The Purchase Decision Variable (Y) is influenced in various ways degree by the variables Price (X1), Promotion (X2), Location (X3), and Interest Buy (Z).

• *Q² Predictive Relevance:*

Is known from results calculation that more Q square values big of 0. It is show that mark observation has reconstructed with Correct so that provide a predictive relevance model. For endogenous latent variable, p This show that structural model own influence relatively of 99.94% against measurement observational, with possibility model error of 0.06%.

➤ *Pen g Exam Hypothesis:*

In study This used t values, p values, and coefficients track For test hypothesis. Coefficient path and the value of t can used for determine significance and prediction testing hypothesis (Kock, N. 2016). p value can used For evaluate prediction and significance in testing hypothesis, according to Kock, N. (2016). The values in table -t can seen in the table below this.

Table 6 T- table values

	<i>One tailed</i>	<i>Two tailed</i>
T- table	1.64	1.96

Got t- table value as following, as stated by Kock, N. (2016), with level 95% confidence (5% alpha), two tailed:

- H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted If t- statistical value more big of 1.96 is considered influence direct.
- H0 is accepted and H1 is rejected If t- statistical value (used For influence direct) less from 1.96.

➤ *Influence Price Against Interest Buy House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci:*

Hypothesis study First reads: "Prices matter to interest buy House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci". And from hypothesis.

This developed become hypothesis statistics as following:

- H_{0.1}: $\gamma_1 = 0$: Prices are not influential to interest buy House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci;
- H_{1.1}: $\gamma_1 \neq 0$: Price matters to interest buy House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci.

In addition, by using the SmartPLS software and the bootstrap method, hypothesis testing based on the previous hypothesis produces the following values:

Table 7 Path coefficient and t-count Effect of Price on Interest Buy House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci

Influence	Original Sample (O)	t- Statistics	p-values	Conclusion
Price Against Interest Buy	0.316	2,200	0.028	Reject H _{0.1}

Source: Data Processing (2022)

In Table 7 obtained mark *Original Sample (O)* ie as big 0.316 show that direction influence from price to interest buy House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci is positive or the same way, that is the more in accordance or affordable price so it's increasing interest buy House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci. Price effect to interest buy House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci is significant, with t- statistical value as big 2,200 more big from t table or $2.200 > 1.96$, and mark *p-value* as big 0.028 more _ small of alpha 5% (0.05). With thereby then H_{1.1} accepted It means **price influential to interest buy House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci**.

According to a number of study before, result in accordance with research conducted, where _ mention that interest buy consumer to A property like the house is determined by the level suitability price (Ciamas . ES, Hutabarat & Sulaiman (2021), Siagian, Idahwati & Ginting (2022). Concept price Alone is A utility, where matter This related with to what extent A stuff, deep matter This home, got fulfil needs, wants, and satisfaction consumer (Rani, 2018). because _ that's interest buy consumer House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci can strengthen when consumer feel that House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci

own appropriate price _ or worth it with fulfillment need , want , and give satisfaction for consumer (Yolanda & Abdullah, 2021), because price No only limited numbers , but represent A function from product to be bought (Subagio, 2020).

➤ *Influence Promotion to Interest Buy House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci:*

Hypothesis study First reads : " Promotion influential to interest buy House *Sandalwood Homes* Lippo Karawaci ". And from hypothesis.

This developed become hypothesis statistics as following :

- $H_{0.2} : \gamma_2 = 0$: Promotion No influential to interest buy House *Sandalwood Homes* Lippo Karawaci ;
- $H_{1.2} : \gamma_2 \neq 0$: Promotion influential to interest buy House *Sandalwood Homes* Lippo Karawaci.

By using the SmartPLS software and the bootstrap method, hypothesis testing based on the hypothesis above produces the following values:

Table 8 Path coefficient and t-count Effect Promotion To Interest Buy House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci

Influence	Original Sample (O)	t- Statistics	p-values	Conclusion
Promotion To Interest Buy	0.348	2,409	0.016	Reject $H_{0.2}$

Source : Data Processing (2022)

From the results table above _ obtained mark *Original Sample* (O) ie as big 0.348 show that direction influence from promotion to interest buy House *Sandalwood Homes* Lippo Karawaci is positive or the same way , that is the more Good promotion so it 's increasing interest buy House *Sandalwood Homes* Lippo Karawaci . With a t-statistic value of 2.409 greater than t table or 2.409 greater than 1.96 and a p-value of 0.016 lower than alpha 5% (0.05), promotion has a significant effect on buyer interest in Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci. With thereby then $H_{1.2}$ accepted It means **promotion influential to interest buy House *Sandalwood Homes* Lippo Karawaci** .

According to a number of study before , result in accordance with research conducted , where _ mention that interest buy consumer can increase moment promotion done with good (Apriliani & Kusumastuti, 2019; Rahman & Widarko, 2020; Saputra , Yuliana & Nasution , 2022). Height interest buy consumer Because promotion This can showed with the more height attention , interest , desire , as well action consumer to House *Sandalwood Homes* Lippo Karawaci . Promotion done No only limited to advertising, but also related with promotion targeted sales _ increase sale House *Sandalwood Homes* Lippo Karawaci , build connection Good with consumer . With so , can understood that promotion own role important in increase interest buy consumer.

➤ *Influence Location Against Interest Buy House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci:*

Hypothesis study First reads : "Location matters to interest buy House *Sandalwood Homes* Lippo Karawaci ". And from hypothesis.

This developed become hypothesis statistics as following :

- $H_{0.3} : \gamma_3 = 0$: Location no influential to interest buy House *Sandalwood Homes* Lippo Karawaci ;
- $H_{1.3} : \gamma_3 \neq 0$: Location matters to interest buy House *Sandalwood Homes* Lippo Karawaci.

By using the SmartPLS software and the bootstrap method, hypothesis testing based on the hypothesis above produces the following values:

Table 9 Path coefficient and t-count Effect of Location on Interest Buy House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci

Influence	Original Sample (O)	t- Statistics	p-values	Conclusion
Location Against Interest Buy	0.334	2,509	0.012	Reject $H_{0.3}$

Source: Data Processing (2022)

In Table 9 obtained mark *Original Sample* (O) ie as big 0.334 show that direction influence from location to interest buy House *Sandalwood Homes* Lippo Karawaci is positive or the same way , that is the more Good location so it 's increasing interest buy House *Sandalwood Homes* Lippo Karawaci . At Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci, location has a significant effect on buyer interest, with a t-statistic value of 2.509 greater than t table or 2.509 greater than 1.96 and a p-value of 0.012 lower than alpha 5% (0.05). Then $H_{1.3}$ accepted It means **location influential to interest buy House *Sandalwood Homes* Lippo Karawaci**.

According to a number of study before , result in accordance with research conducted , where _ mention that interest buy consumer will depend from location (Dicky, 2021; Indah Rahmawati, 2021). this _ related with how consumer consider convenience to be accepted , or A received benefits _ when A products and services , deep matter This is House with all

accessibility , yes give convenience for consumer The more strategic location housing area the so the more tall level request will housing area (Alvionita , 2020; Sembiring & Sunargo , 2022).

➤ *Influence Price Against Purchasing Decisions House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci:*

Hypothesis study First reads : “Prices matter to decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* ”. And from hypothesis.

This developed become hypothesis statistics as following :

- $H_{0.4} : \gamma_1 = 0$: Prices are not influential to decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* ;
- $H_{1.4} : \gamma_1 \neq 0$: Price matters to decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci*.

By using the SmartPLS software and the bootstrap method, hypothesis testing based on the hypothesis above produces the following values:

Table 10 Path coefficient and t-count Effect of Price on Purchasing Decisions House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci

Influence	Original Sample (O)	t- Statistics	p-values	Conclusion
Price Against Purchase Decision	0.497	2,509	0.012	Reject $H_{0.4}$

Source: Data Processing (2022)

In Table 10, values *Original Sample (O)* ie as big 0.497 show that direction influence from price to decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* is positive or the same way, that is the more in accordance or affordable price so it 's increasing decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* . With a t-statistic value of 2.509 greater than t table or 2.509 greater than 1.96 and a p-value of 0.012 lower than alpha 5% (0.05), the purchase decision for Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci is significantly influenced by price. With thereby then $H_{1.4}$ accepted It means **price influential to decision purchase House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci**.

According to a number of study earlier , also mentioned that decision purchase , deep matter This is House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* , is determined by the degree to which consumer evaluate House the based on the price (Hidayat, 2020; Imalia & Aprileny, 2020). The more how strong decision purchase consequence price the can reviewed from accordingly hope consumer to what marketing has to offer , is visit return from consumers , and consumers who recommend House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci to friends , relatives , and relatives.

➤ *Influence Promotion Against Purchasing Decisions House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci*

Hypothesis study First reads : " Promotion influential to decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* ”. And from hypothesis.

This developed become hypothesis statistics as following:

- $H_{0.5} : \gamma_2 = 0$: Promotion No influential to decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* ;
- $H_{1.5} : \gamma_2 \neq 0$: Promotion influential to decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci*.

By using the SmartPLS software and the bootstrap method, hypothesis testing based on the hypothesis above produces the following values:

Table 11 Path coefficient and t-count Influence Promotion Against Purchasing Decisions House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci

Influence	Original Sample (O)	t- Statistics	p-values	Conclusion
Promotion Against Purchase Decision	- 0.178	1,388	0.166	Accept $H_{0.5}$

Source: Data Processing (2022)

From Table 11 obtained mark *Original Sample (O)* ie of -0.178 _ show that direction influence from promotion to decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* is negative or opposite , meaning the more Good promotion hence the lower the decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* . With a t-statistic value of 1.388 which is less than t table or 1.388 less than 1.96, and a p-value of 0.166 which is greater than alpha 5% (0.05), the effect of promotion on the decision to buy Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci is not significant. Then $H_{1.5}$ rejected It means **promotion No influential to decision purchase House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci**.

According to study before, result in accordance with research conducted , where _ mention that in make decision purchase , promotion No consideration mainly for consumer For buy house (Yunaida & Hanum, 2019). it _ can happen Because in buy A deep house _ matter This is House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* , consumers No only consider promotions provided by the

marketing team , however there is thing to be consideration important consumers , for one is suitability price with quality House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci*.

➤ *Influence Location Against Purchasing Decisions House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci:*

Hypothesis study First reads : “Location matters to decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* ”. And from hypothesis.

This developed become hypothesis statistics as following :

- $H_{0.6} : \gamma_3 = 0$: Location no influential to decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* ;
- $H_{1.6} : \gamma_3 \neq 0$: Location matters to decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* .

By using the SmartPLS software and the bootstrap method, hypothesis testing based on the hypothesis above produces the following values:

Table 12 Path coefficient and t-count Effect of Location on Purchasing Decisions House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci

Influence	Original Sample (O)	t- Statistics	p-values	Conclusion
Location Against Purchasing Decisions	0.019	0.348	0.728	Accept $H_{0.6}$

Source : Data Processing (2022)

In Table 12, values *Original Sample (O)* ie of - 0.019 show that direction influence from location to decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* is negative or opposite direction , meaning the more Good location hence the lower the decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* . Location influence to decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* is No significant , with t- statistical value as big 0.348 more small from t table or $0.348 < 1.96$, and mark *p-value* as big 0.728 more _ big of alpha 5% (0.05) . Then , $H_{1.6}$ rejected It means **location No influential to decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci*** .

According to study before , result in accordance with research conducted , where _ mention that location No influential to decision purchase (Nursiyono & Dewi, 2021). it _ can happen Because in buy A home , consumer No only consider the location given by the marketing team , however there is other things to be consideration important consumer . Consumer Possible just interested with location is there , however other things also become considerations , such as price . Because , location a strategic house will also make price House the become more tall compared to House with less location _ strategic .

➤ *Influence Interest Buy Against Purchasing Decisions House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci:*

Hypothesis study First reads : " Interest buy influential to decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* ”. And from hypothesis.

This developed become hypothesis statistics as following :

- $H_{0.7} : \beta = 0$: Interest buy No influential to decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* ;
- $H_{1.7} : \beta \neq 0$: Interest buy influential to decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci*.

By using the SmartPLS software and the bootstrap method, hypothesis testing based on the hypothesis above produces the following values:

Table 13 Path coefficient and t-count Influence Interest Buy Against Purchasing Decisions House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci

Influence	Original Sample (O)	t- Statistics	p-values	Conclusion
Interest Buy Against Purchase Decision	0.688	4,494	0.000	Reject $H_{0.7}$

Source : Data Processing (2022)

The Original Sample (O) value of 0.688 indicates that decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* influenced in a manner positive or in the direction of interest buy . this _ show that decision buyer For Buying *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* House is influenced by the level intention buy it . With a *p-value* of 0.000 or more small of alpha 5% (0.05) and a t- statistic value of 4.494 more big from t table or 4,494 more big of 1.96, decision purchase *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* in a manner significant influenced by interests buy .With thus $H_{1.7}$ is

accepted which shows that decision purchase House *Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci* influenced by interests buy.

According to study before , result in accordance with research conducted , where _ mention that decision purchase consumer determined by the height interest buy consumer to A property (Redjo, Wijayaningtyas, & Iskandar, 2019; Yordan, Zulkarnain, & Alwie, 2019). this _ show that when consumer has own attention , interest , high desire _ to

House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci , then will increase level decision purchase . The more how strong decision purchase the can reviewed from accordingly hope consumer to what marketing has to offer , is visit return from consumers , and consumers who recommend House Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci to friends , relatives , and relatives

B. Discussion:

➤ *The Influence of Prices on Buying Interest at Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci:*

Based on the findings of the analysis that has been carried out, the Original Sample (O) value is 0.316 indicating that the direction of price influence on the intention to buy Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci is positive or unidirectional. This means that the greater the price, the greater the interest in buying a house. Lippo Karawaci of Sandalwood Homes At Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci the effect of price on buying interest is significant, with a t-statistic value of 2.200 greater than t table or 2.200 greater than 1.96 and a p-value of 0.028 lower than alpha 5% (0 , 05). Therefore, H1.1 is accepted which shows that the intention to buy Rumah Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci is influenced by price.

The results show that price has a significant influence on purchase intention, with a positive direction of influence indicating that the more affordable the price is specified by consumers, the more appropriate the price is for the quality of existing housing, the more appropriate the price is for the benefits consumers receive, and the more competitive the price of the house being offered, then this will lead to higher buying interest, which is indicated by the increasing attention, interest, desire, and consumer action towards the Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci house. Several studies also show that consumer buying interest in a property such as a house is largely determined by the level of suitability of the price (Ciamas. ES, Hutabarat & Sulaiman (2021), Siagian, Idahwati & Ginting (2022). The concept of price itself is a utility, where this relates to the extent to which an item, which in this case is a house, can meet the needs, wants, and satisfy consumers (Rani, 2018). Therefore, consumer buying interest can strengthen when consumers feel that an item/service has an appropriate or commensurate price by fulfilling needs, wants, and providing satisfaction for consumers (Yolanda & Abdullah, 2021), because price is not just a number, but represents a function of the product to be purchased (Subagio, 2020).

➤ *The Effect of Promotion on Buying Interests at Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci:*

From the results of the analysis it can be seen that the Original Sample (O) value is 0.348 indicating that the direction of promotion influence on the intention to buy Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci is positive or unidirectional. That is, the better the promotion, the more interest in buying Sandalwood Homes. Karawaci Lippo With a t-statistic value of 2.409 greater than t table or 2.409 greater than 1.96 and a p-value of 0.016 lower than alpha 5% (0.05), promotion has a significant effect on buyer

interest at Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci. As a result, H1.2 is accepted which shows that promotions have an effect on customer buying interest at Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci.

The results showing that promotion has a significant and positive effect on purchase intention means that when advertising is more intensively carried out, direct marketing is carried out better, sales promotion is more diverse and attractive, relations with the community are getting better, and personal selling is getting more intense , it will increase consumer buying interest in the house. The high interest in buying consumers because of this promotion can be shown by the increasing attention, interest, desire, and consumer action towards Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci. In marketing, promotion plays a very important role so that product information can be conveyed in an interesting way, and can be well received by consumers. Promotion is carried out not only limited to advertising, but also related to sales promotion which aims to increase sales, build good relations with consumers. Several studies confirm the results of this study, where consumer buying interest can increase when promotions are carried out well (Apriliani & Kusumastuti, 2019; Rahman & Widarko, 2020; Saputra, Yuliana & Nasution, 2022). Thus, it can be understood that promotion has an important role in increasing consumer buying interest.

➤ *The Effect of Location on Buying Interests at Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci:*

The results of the analysis show that the Original Sample (O) value is 0.334 indicating that the direction of the influence of location on the intention to buy Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci is positive or unidirectional, this indicates that the better the location, the greater the interest to buy. bought Sandalwood Homes. Karawaci Lippo At Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci location has a significant effect on buyer interest, with a t-statistic value of 2.509 greater than t table or 2.509 greater than 1.96 and a p-value of 0.012 lower than alpha 5% (0.05) . Thus, H1.3 is accepted which shows that the decision to purchase a house at Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci is influenced by location.

The results show that location has a significant influence on buying interest, with a positive direction of influence meaning that a house has a house in a strategic location with various Toll, Mall, Hospital, Worship and educational facilities, which are delivered clearly and in detail by the marketing team , with the ability of the marketing team to respond well and empathize with consumer conditions, this will strengthen or increase consumer buying interest in homes. The high interest in buying consumers because of this location can be shown by the increasing attention, interest, desire, and consumer action towards the Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci house. The results of this study are also supported by several previous studies, where consumer buying interest will depend on location. This relates to how consumers consider the convenience to be received, or a benefit received when a product and service, which in this case is a house with all its accessibility, can provide convenience for consumers

(Dicky, 2021; Indah Rahmawati, 2021). What is meant by "location" is the physical location chosen by the developer company to build housing. Because consumer interest in buying a house is strongly influenced by the location of where you live, location is an important factor in the competition to attract customers. The higher the level of demand for housing, the more strategic the location (Alvionita, 2020; Sembiring & Sunargo, 2022).

➤ *The Influence of Prices on the Purchase Decision of Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci Houses:*

The results of the analysis show that the Original Sample (O) value is 0.497 indicating that the direction of price influence on the purchasing decision of Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci is positive or unidirectional. This means that the higher the decision to buy a Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci house, the more appropriate or affordable the price is. With a t-statistic value of 2.509 greater than t table or 2.509 greater than 1.96 and a p-value of 0.012 lower than alpha 5% (0.05), the purchase decision for Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci is significantly influenced by price. Thus H1.4 is accepted which shows that the decision to purchase a Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci house is influenced by price.

The findings show that price has a significant and beneficial effect on purchasing decisions. This means that consumers will be more confident in making purchasing decisions if the price of the house offered is more competitive, more affordable, and more in line with the quality of the existing house and the benefits it provides. The stronger purchasing decisions due to these prices can be seen from the conformity of consumer expectations of what marketing has to offer, the presence of return visits from consumers, and consumers who recommend the Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci house to friends, relatives and relatives. The results of this analysis are supported by findings from previous studies, where purchasing decisions, which in this case are houses, are determined by the extent to which consumers value the house based on its price (Hidayat, 2020; Imalia & Aprileny, 2020). Price will always be a factor in the buying and selling of goods or services between consumers and producers. While consumers need products that meet their requirements and usually buy products based on their purchasing power, producers can determine the price of the products they sell in order to make a profit (Senggetang, Mandey, & Moniharapon, 2019; Kumala & Anwar, 2020).

➤ *The Effect of Promotion on the Decision to Purchase a House, Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci:*

The results of the analysis show that the Original Sample (O) value is -0.178 indicating that the effect of promotion on the purchasing decision of Rumah Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci is negative or in the opposite direction. This means that the better the promotion, the lower the purchasing decision for Rumah Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci. With a t-statistic value of 1.388 which is smaller than t table or 1.388 $\pm$ 1.96, and a p-value of 0.166 which is greater than alpha 5% (0.05), the effect of promotion on the decision to buy Sandalwood Homes Lippo

Karawaci is not significant. As a result, H1.5 was rejected, indicating that the promotion had nothing to do with whether or not Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci House was bought or not.

The results show that promotion does not have a significant impact or influence on purchasing decisions, meaning that when advertising is more intensively carried out, direct marketing is carried out better, sales promotion is more diverse and interesting, relations with the community are getting better, and personal selling which is increasingly intense, then this will not increase consumer purchasing decisions for homes. This can happen because in buying a house, consumers do not only consider the promotions provided by the marketing team, but there are other things that are important considerations for consumers. In other words, promotion is not something that is effective so that consumers can make purchasing decisions at Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci. Consumers do not pay attention to the promotions given when deciding to buy a house, but there are other things that are taken into consideration, which is in accordance with several previous studies which explain that in making purchasing decisions, promotions are not the main consideration for consumers to buy a house (Yunaida & Hanum, 2019). The results of the analysis are contrary to previous research, where promotion influences purchase decisions (Angelica, 2020; Tabroni & Komarudin, 2021).

➤ *The Effect of Location on the Decision to Buy a House at Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci:*

The results of the analysis show that the Original Sample (O) value is -0.019 indicating that the direction of the influence of location on the purchasing decision of Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci is negative or in the opposite direction. This means that the decision to buy a house at Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci is lower if the location is better. With a t-statistic value of 0.348 which is smaller than t table or 0.348 $\pm$ 1.96, and a p-value of 0.728, which is greater than alpha 5% (0.05), the effect of location on the decision to buy Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci is not significant. As a result, H1.6 is rejected, indicating that location has no effect on the buyer's decision to buy the Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci residence.

The results show that location does not have a significant influence on purchasing decisions, meaning that a house has a house with a strategic location with various Toll, Mall, Hospital, Worship and educational facilities, which are delivered clearly and in detail by the marketing team, with the ability a marketing team that can respond well and empathize with consumer conditions, this will not strengthen consumer purchasing decisions regarding prices. This can happen because in buying a house, consumers do not only consider the location provided by the marketing team, but there are other things that are important considerations for consumers. In other words, location is not an effective factor for consumers to make purchasing decisions at Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci. Consumers may be interested in the existing location, but other things are also considered, such as price. This is because a strategic

location of a house will also make the price of the house higher than a house with a less strategic location (Nursiyono & Dewi, 2021), so that consumers will consider their capabilities before deciding to buy a house.

➤ *The Effect of Buying Interest on the Decision to Buy a House at Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci:*

The Original Sample (O) value of 0.688 indicates that the direction of the influence of buying interest on the purchasing decision of Rumah Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci is positive or unidirectional. This means that the higher the interest in buying, the higher the decision to buy a house. The findings of the analysis can be seen from these findings. Lippo Karawaci from Sandalwood Homes With a t-statistical value of 4.494 greater than t table or 4.494 greater than 1.96 and a p-value of 0.000 is smaller than the alpha of 5% (0.05), the decision to buy Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci is significantly influenced by buying interest. Thus H1.7 is accepted which shows that the decision to purchase Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci is influenced by buying interest.

The results show that buying interest has a significant influence on purchasing decisions, with a positive influence direction. This shows that when consumers have high attention, interest, desire for Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci houses, this will increase the level of purchasing decisions. The stronger the purchase decision can be seen from the conformity of consumer expectations of what marketing has to offer, the presence of return visits from consumers, and consumers who recommend the Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci house to friends, relatives and relatives. The results of this analysis are also in accordance with several previous studies, where consumer purchasing decisions are determined by high consumer buying interest in a property (Redjo, Wijayaningtyas, & Iskandar, 2019; Yordan, Zulkarnain, & Alwie, 2019).

V. CONCLUSION

➤ *The following are the conclusions of the research based on the results of the analysis and discussion described:*

- Prices affect the intention to buy Rumah Cendana Homes at PT. Lippo Karawaci. This shows that the more appropriate or affordable the price, the more interest in buying the Sandalwood Homes Lippo Karawaci House.
- Promotion has an effect on the intention to buy Rumah Cendana Homes at PT. Lippo Karawaci. This shows that the better the promotion, the greater the interest in buying Rumah Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci.
- Location influences the intention to buy Rumah Cendana Homes at PT. Lippo Karawaci. This shows that the better the location, the more interest in buying the Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci house
- Prices affect the purchase decision to buy a Cendana Homes House at PT. Lippo Karawaci. This shows that the more appropriate or affordable the price, the more it will increase the purchasing decision for the Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci House.

- Promotion has an effect on the purchasing decision of Cendana Homes Houses at PT. Lippo Karawaci. This shows that the better the promotion does not increase the purchasing decision for Rumah Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci.
- Location influences the decision to buy a Cendana Homes House at PT. Lippo Karawaci. This shows that the better the location, the better the decision to purchase the Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci House.
- Buying interest influences the decision to buy a Cendana Homes House at PT. Lippo Karawaci. This shows that the higher the purchase intention, the higher the decision to purchase the Cendana Homes Lippo Karawaci House.

Suggestions for this research are divided in two aspects, namely from an academic aspect and a practical aspect.

The researcher hopes that the next research can examine and study the phenomenon of purchasing decisions for property by adding lifestyle variables. In an effort to increase the purchasing decision of Cendana Homes, based on the results of the analysis, among others: Cendana Homes at PT. Lippo Karawaci should not focus on promotion and dissemination of location-related information. This is because the results of the analysis show that promotion and location are not significant in influencing purchasing decisions. However, the attractive price offers made consumers decide to make purchases at Cendana Homes houses. Cendana Homes at PT. Lippo Karawaci can optimize price variables, such as offering varying house prices. However, this study also shows that there is an influence of buying interest on purchasing decisions, where buying interest is influenced by promotion, price, and location. Therefore, in an effort to increase buying interest, Cendana Homes at PT. Lippo Karawaci can offer a more diverse range of promotional prices, which apply to all types of consumers according to their level of ability.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Alvionita, V. (2020). Pengaruh Promosi, Harga, Lokasi, Kualitas Bangunan, Dan Fasilitas Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Rumah Di Gresik Residence (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Muhammadiyah Gresik)
- [2]. Ciamas, W. S., Ciamas, E. S., L. L., Hutabarat, F. A., & Sulaiman, F. (2021). Harga sebagai Komponen Marketing Mix Terhadap Penjualan di PT Bale Dipa Aruna (Perumahan Medan Resort City), Medan. In Seminar Nasional Sains dan Teknologi Informasi (SENSASI) (Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 496-500).
- [3]. Ghozali, Imam, Hengky Latan. 2015. Konsep, Teknik, Aplikasi Menggunakan Smart PLS 3.0 Untuk Penelitian Empiris. BP Undip. Semarang.
- [4]. Hair, J.F., Hult, G.T.M., Ringle, C.M. and Sarstedt, M. (2017a), A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), Sage, Thousand Oaks, CA
- [5]. Kotler, P. 2013. Manajemen Pemasaran, Jakarta: Penerbit : Erlangga.

- [6]. Kotler, Philip and Keller, Kevin Lane. 2013. Manajemen Pemasaran, Jilid 1, Edisi 13, Jakarta: Erlangga
- [7]. Kotler, P, Bowen, J.T & Makens, J. 2014. Marketing for Hospitality and Tourism: Sixth Edition. London: Pearson Education Limited.
- [8]. Sembiring, E. F., & Sunargo, S. (2022). Pengaruh harga, promosi dan lokasi terhadap keputusan pembelian rumah KPR subsidi di PT Sinar Jaya Putra Kampar Batam. *Jurnal Paradigma Ekonomika*, 17(1), 117-126.
- [9]. Rahmawati, R. 2013. Peranan Bauran Pemasaran (Marketing Mix) Terhadap peningkatan Penjualan. (Online), Vol. 2, No. 2, diakses 12 April 2019). [10]. Dinar Standard. (2021). State of the Global Islamic Economy Report 2020/2021. State of the Global Islamic Economy Report 2020/21, 4–202.
- [10]. Subagio, J. (2020). Analisis Pengaruh Desain Produk, Kualitas Produk Dan Kepercayaan Merek Terhadap Minat Beli Konsumen Atas Produk Mobil Xpander Dengan Harga Sebagai Variabel Moderating (Studi Pada PT. SARDANA INDAH BERLIAN MOTOR). Kumpulan Karya Ilmiah Mahasiswa Fakultas S.
- [11]. Sembiring, E. F., & Sunargo, S. (2022). Pengaruh harga, promosi dan lokasi terhadap keputusan pembelian rumah KPR subsidi di PT Sinar Jaya Putra Kampar Batam. *Jurnal Paradigma Ekonomika*, 17(1), 117-126.
- [12]. Tjiptono, Fandy & Chandra. 2016. Service, Quality dan Satisfaction. Yogyakarta: Andi Offset.
- [13]. Yolanda, R. E., & Abdullah, M. F. (2021). Pengaruh Harga, Promosi, Dan Kemudahan Bertransaksi Terhadap Minat Menggunakan Layanan Mobile Payment Go-Pay Selama Pandemi. *Journal of Financial Economics & Investment*, 1(1), 59-70.
- [14]. Yamin, Sofyan dan Heri Kurniawan. 2011. Generasi Baru Mengolah Data Penelitian dengan Partial Least Square Path Modeling: Aplikasi dengan Software XLSTAT, SmartPLS, dan Visual PLS. Salemba Infotek. Jakarta.